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ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF METFORMIN AND TENELIGLIPTIN IN BULK AND ITS DOSAGE FORM USING RP-HPLC

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ABSTRACT

A new method was developed for simultaneous estimation of Teneligliptin and Metformin by RP-HPLC. The chromatographic conditions were successfully carried out on Inertsil ODS column C8 (4.6x250mm) of 5µm particle size, flow rate was 1.0ml/min, using mobile phase composed of 50% buffer: 50% Acetonitrile, detection wavelength used as 240 nm. The instruments and materials used were WATERS, software: Empower, 2695 separation module. 2487 UV detector, UV/VIS spectrophotometer-LABINDIA UV 3000⁺. The retention time was found to be for Metformin 3.608 min and for Teneligliptin 5.148 min. The assay of Metformin and Teneligliptin was performed with tablets and the % assay was found to be 99.97 and 100.64 which shows that the method is useful for routine analysis. The linearity of Metformin and Teneligliptin was found to be linear with a correlation coefficient of 0.999 and 0.999, which shows that the method is capable of producing good sensitivity. The acceptance criteria of precision is RSD should be not more than 2.0% and the method show precision 0.4 and 0.8 for Metformin and Teneligliptin which shows that the method is precise. The acceptance criteria of intermediate precision is RSD should be not more than 2.0% and the method show precision 0.1 and 0.7 for Metformin and Teneligliptin which shows that the method is repeatable when performed in different days also. The accuracy limit is the percentage recovery should be in the range of 97.0% - 103.0%. The total recovery was found to be 99.86% and 99.96% for Metformin and Teneligliptin. The validation of developed method shows that the accuracy is well within the limit, which shows that the method is capable of showing good accuracy and reproducibility. The acceptance criteria for LOD and LOQ is 3 and 10. The LOD and LOQ for Metformin was found to be 3.00 and 9.98 and LOD and LOQ for Teneligliptin was found to be 3.02 and 10.00. The linearity of Teneligliptin and Metformin was found to be linear with a correlation coefficient of (R²) 0.998 and 0.999 respectively. The robustness limit for mobile phase variation and flow rate variation are well within the limit, which shows that the method is having good system suitability and precision under given set of conditions. The analytical method was validated according to ICH Guidelines.

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INTRODUCTION**METFORMIN****Description:**

Metformin is a biguanide antihyperglycemic agent used for treating non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM). It improves glycemic control by decreasing hepatic glucose production, decreasing glucose absorption and increasing insulin-mediated glucose uptake.

Structure:

IUPAC Name	:	1-carbamimidamido-N, N-dimethylmethanimidamide
Molecular Formula	:	C ₄ H ₁₁ N ₅
Mol. mass	:	129.1636 g/mol
Category	:	Antidiabetic Agents
Appearance	:	White Crystalline powder
Melting Point	:	223-226°C
Solubility	:	It is soluble in Water and Ethanol

Mechanism of action:

Metformin's mechanisms of action differ from other classes of oral antihyperglycemic agents. Metformin decreases blood glucose levels by decreasing hepatic glucose production, decreasing intestinal absorption of glucose, and improving insulin sensitivity by increasing peripheral glucose uptake and utilization. These effects are mediated by the initial activation by metformin of AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK), a liver enzyme that plays an important role in insulin signaling, whole body energy balance, and the metabolism of glucose and fats. Activation of AMPK is required for metformin's inhibitory effect on the production of glucose by liver cells. Increased peripheral utilization of glucose may be due to improved insulin binding to insulin receptors. Metformin administration also increases AMPK activity in skeletal muscle. AMPK is known to cause GLUT4 deployment to the plasma membrane, resulting in insulin-independent glucose uptake. The rare side effect, lactic acidosis, is thought to be caused by decreased liver uptake of serum lactate, one of the substrates of gluconeogenesis. In those with healthy renal function, the slight excess is simply cleared. However, those with severe renal impairment may accumulate clinically significant serum lactic acid levels. Other conditions that may precipitate

TENELIGLIPTIN**Description:**

Teneligliptin is a pharmaceutical drug for the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus. It belongs to the class of anti-diabetic drugs known as dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitors or "gliptins"

Structure:**PHYSICOCHEMICAL DATA:**

Formula	:	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ N ₆ OS
Molecular weight	:	426.58 g/mol
Melting point	:	188-190 °C
Solubility	:	Soluble in Dimethyl sulfoxide

Mechanism of action:

The mechanism of DPP-4 inhibitors is to increase incretion levels (GLP-1 and GIP), which inhibit glucagon release, which in turn increases insulin secretion, decreases gastric emptying, and decreases blood glucose levels. Ashim Kumar Sen (2016); Shailesh V. Luhar (2016).

The literature review reveals that few HPLC methods for the estimation of Metformin and Teneligliptin alone and in combination with other drugs. Very few methods are reported for estimation of both drugs from formulation. We intend to develop RP-HPLC method by simultaneous determination with simple, rapid, greater sensitivity and faster elution.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD**Table 1: Instruments used.**

SL. No	Instrument	Model
1	HPLC	WATERS, software: Empower, 2695 separation module.2487 UV detector.
2	UV/VIS spectrophotometer	LABINDIA UV 3000 ⁺
3	pH meter	Adwa – AD 1020
4	Weighing machine	Afcoset ER-200A
5	Pipettes and Burettes	Borosil
6	Beakers	Borosil

Table 2: Chemicals used.

SL.No	Chemical	Brand
1	Metformin	Supplied by Pharmatrain
2	Teneligliptin	Supplied by Pharmatrain
3	KH ₂ PO ₄	FINAR chemical LTD
4	Water and Methanol for HPLC	Standard solutions Ltd
5	Acetonitrile for HPLC	Standard solutions Ltd
6	HCl, H ₂ O ₂ , NaOH	MERCK

Chromatographic conditions**OPTIMIZED CHROMATOGRAPHIC CONDITIONS:**

Instrument used	:	High performance liquid chromatography equipped with Auto Sampler and DAD or UV detector
Temperature	:	Ambient
Column	:	Inertsil ODS column C8 (4.6 x 250mm, 5µm)
Buffer	:	Phosphate buffer pH 3
Mobile phase	:	50% buffer: 50% Acetonitrile
Flow rate	:	1.0 ml per min
Wavelength	:	240 nm
Injection volume	:	20 µl
Run time	:	12min.

Wave length selection:

UV spectrum of 10 µg / ml Metformin and Teneligliptin in diluents (mobile phase composition) was recorded by scanning in the range of 200nm to 400nm. From the UV spectrum wavelength selected as 240nm. At this wavelength both the drugs show good absorbance.

Optimization of Column:

Inertsil ODS column C8 (4.6 x 250mm, 5µm) was found to be ideal as it gave good peak shape and resolution at 1.0 ml/min flow.

Preparation of standard solutions:

Accurately weigh and transfer 125 mg of Metformin and 5 mg of Teneligliptin working standard into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask add about 7 mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.6 ml of the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Sample Solution Preparation:

Accurately weigh 10 tablets crush in mortar and pestle and transfer equivalent to 125 mg of Metformin and 5 mg Teneligliptin sample into a 10 mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7 mL of Diluent and sonicate it up to 10 mins to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. Then it is Filtered through 0.44 micron Injection filter. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.6ml of Metformin and Teneligliptin from the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Method Development: Chromatographic conditions:**

Column : Inertsil ODS column C8 (4.6 x 250mm, 5 μ m)
 Mobile phase : Phosphate buffer pH 3: Acetonitrile (50:50)
 Flow rate : 1 ml per min
 Wavelength : 240 nm
 Injection volume : 20 μ l
 Run time : 12min

Figure 1: Optimized Method.**Table 3: Optimized parameters.**

S. No	Name	RT(min)	Area (μ V sec)	Height (μ V)	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Metformin	3.608	854796	71179		1.14	3281.91
2	Teneligliptin	5.148	114853	7911	5.75	1.08	5125.30

Observation:

The chromatogram is perfect with clear separation of components. The peak symmetry and system suitability parameters are within the limits. Hence this method is chosen as optimized one.

Table 4: System suitability parameters.

S. No	Name	RT(min)	Area (μ V sec)	Height (μ V)	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Metformin	3.608	854796	71179		1.14	3281.91
2	Teneligliptin	5.148	114853	7911	5.75	1.08	5125.30

Acceptance criteria:

- Resolution between two drugs must be not less than 2.
- Theoretical plates must be not less than 2000.
- Tailing factor must be not more than 2.
- It was found from above data that all the system suitability parameters for developed method were within the limit.

Method Validation:**ASSAY:**

Standard and sample solution injected as described under experimental work. The corresponding chromatograms and results are shown below.

Figure 2: Chromatogram for Standard.

Figure 3: Chromatogram for Sample.

ACCURACY:

Sample solutions at different concentrations (50%, 100%, and 150%) were prepared and the % recovery was calculated.

Figure 4: Chromatogram for Accuracy 50%.

PRECISION:

Precision of the method was carried out for both sample solutions as described under experimental work. The corresponding chromatograms and results are shown below.

Figure 5: Chromatogram for precision.

Table 5: Results of Precision for Metformin.

Injection	Area
Injection-1	852828
Injection-2	852337
Injection-3	858355
Injection-4	852839
Injection-5	858513
Injection-6	857582
Average	855409.0
Standard Deviation	12.524.5
%RSD	0.4

Table 6: Results of Precision for Tenueligliptin.

Injection	Area
Injection-1	111368
Injection-2	112717
Injection-3	112655
Injection-4	113939
Injection-5	112513
Injection-6	112282
Average	112662.3
Standard Deviation	845.7
%RSD	0.8

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

LINEARITY:

The linearity range was found to lie from 250µg/ml to 1250µg/ml of Metformin, 10µg/ml to 50µg/ml Of Tenueligliptin and chromatograms are shown below.

Figure 6: Chromatogram for Linearity.

Table 7: Area of different concentration of Metformin and Teneligliptin.

S. No	Metformin		Teneligliptin	
	Concentration (µg/ml)	Area	Concentration (µg/ml)	Area
1	250	244841	10	29672
2	500	525756	20	68336
3	750	856654	30	113345
4	1000	1150925	40	159680
5	1250	1435608	50	204473

Figure 7: Calibration graph for Metformin.

Figure 8: Calibration graph for Teneligliptin.

As per ICH Guidelines, graph of Linearity can be obtained from 5 points.

Table 8: Analytical performance parameters of Metformin and Teneiglipitin.

Parameter	Metformin	Teneiglipitin
Slope (m)	24312	13781
Intercept (c)	50932	51281
Correlation coefficient (R^2)	0.999	0.998

Acceptance criteria:

Correlation coefficient (R^2) should not be less than 0.99

- The correlation coefficient obtained was 0.99 which is in the acceptance limit.

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation(LOQ):

The lowest concentration of the sample was prepared with respect to the base line noise and measured the signal to noise ratio.

Figure 9: Chromatogram of Metformin, Teneiglipitin showing LOD.

Table 9: Results of LOD.

Drug name	Baseline noise(μ V)	Signal obtained (μ V)	S/N ratio
Metformin	66	198	3.00
Teneiglipitin	66	199	3.02

- Signal to noise ratio shall be 3 for LOD solution
- The result obtained is within the limit.

LIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION FOR METFORMIN AND TENELIGLIPTIN

The lowest concentration of the sample was prepared with respect to the base line noise and measured the signal to noise ratio.

Figure 10: Chromatogram of Metformin, Teneiglipitin showing LOQ.

Table 10: Results of LOQ.

Drug name	Baseline noise(μV)	Signal obtained (μV)	S/N ratio
Metformin	66	659	9.98
Teneligliptin	66	660	10.00

- Signal to noise ratio shall be 10 for LOQ solution
- The result obtained is within the limit.

CONCLUSIONS

This method has advantage of simplicity and convenience for the separation and quantitation of Metformin and Teneligliptin in the combination which can be used for the assay of their dosage form. Also, the low solvent consumption and short analytical run time lead to environmentally friendly chromatographic procedure. The method is accurate, precise, rapid and selective for simultaneous estimation of Metformin and Teneligliptin in suspension dosage form. Hence it can be conveniently adopted for routine analysis.

As this method is simple, precise, economical, rapid and can be used for future research work.

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ABBREVIATIONS:

HPLC	-High performance liquid chromatography
$^{\circ}\text{C}$	-Degree centigrade
ICH	-International conference of harmonization
Mg	-Milligram
ml	-Milliliter
RSD	-Relative standard deviation
RT	-Retention time

Conflict of Interest:

There is no conflict of Interest.

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